

UMS
UNIVERSITI MALAYSIA SABAH

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5th International Postgraduate Conference on Biotechnology

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia

**"Symbiosis-science and technology for
sustainable environment towards societal well being"**

8-10 December 2021

ABSTRACT BOOK

UMS KAMPUS RAHMAH
TERAS KECEMERLANGAN DAN KEUNGGULAN

Transformation towards
**UNIVERSITY
INDUSTRY 4.0**

Transforming Ideas into Reality

5th International Postgraduate Conference on Biotechnology

PROGRAMME SCHEDULE

SESSION 2	Theme 1: Natural resources and ecosystem studies <i>Chairperson: Dr. Noor Haliza Binti Hasan @ Ahmad</i>	Theme 2: Environmental management, bio- & eco-engineering technologies and applications <i>Chairperson: Prof. Dr. Victor S. Kuwahara</i>
1100	OTI-4 Andreas Dwi Advento (ITBC, UMS) <i>Conditional Abundance of Asian Weaver Ants (<i>Oecophylla smaragdina</i>) In Oil Palm Plantations under Bagworm Outbreak Occurrence</i>	OTII-4 Mutsumi Sekine (FSE, SU) <i>Effect Of Different Agitation Frequencies on Anaerobic Digestion of Food Waste</i>
1120	OTI-5 Lok Yen Chi (ITBC, UMS) <i>The phylogeny of roundleaf bats (Genus: <i>Hipposideros</i>) in Sabah, Borneo.</i>	OTII-5 Anupreet Kaur Chowdhary (GSSE, SU) <i>Effect Of Transition of Nutritional Modes on Cell Growth in <i>Chromochloris zofingiensis</i></i>
1140	OTI-6 Jauris Salegin (ITBC, UMS) <i>Ethnobotany of the Dusun Labuk People Beluran, Sabah, Malaysia</i>	OTII-6 Ghafur Rahim Mustakim (BMRI, UMS) <i>Effect Of Ultrasonic Frequencies on Removal of Harmful Algal Species, <i>Pyrodinium bahamense</i> Var. <i>Compressum</i></i>
1200	OTI-7 Abdulla-Al-Asif (DASF, UPMB) <i>Macrofaunal diversity on the surface sediment of mangrove habitat adjacent to the seagrass beds of Punang-Sari-River estuary, North-West Borneo, South China Sea</i>	OTII-7 Maria Cecilia Del Rosario Salangsang (GSSE, SU) <i>Starve Them! How to Increase Microbial Cells During Anaerobic Digestion of Solid Waste</i>
1220	Lunch	
1320-1400	Poster Session *PTI-1 to 6	
1400-1440	Keynote presentation Emeritus Professor Dr. Patrick Sorgeloos (Ghent University, Belgium) <i>Chairperson: Chairperson: Assoc. Prof. Ts Dr Sitti Raehanah Muhamad Shaleh</i>	
SESSION 3	Theme 1: Natural resources and ecosystem studies <i>Chairperson: Prof. Dr. Yulinah Trihadiningrum</i>	Theme 2: Environmental management, bio- & eco-engineering technologies and applications <i>Chairperson: Dr. Sandric Leong Chee Yew</i>

OTI-7

Macrofaunal diversity on the surface sediment of mangrove habitat adjacent to the seagrass beds of Punang-Sari-River estuary, North-East Borneo, South China Sea

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Abstract

Macrofaunal diversity and composition are essential components to understand the mangrove ecosystem structures and functions in any dynamic estuarine coast. To understand the temporal benthos community structures, diversity and ecology in the intertidal mangrove forest, this study was conducted from July 2019 to February 2020, in Sarawak (North-East Borneo), specifically in Punang-Sari-River estuary, Lawas, South China Sea. The sampling period was classified as post-monsoon, intermediate-September, pre-monsoon, and monsoon. The mean abundance of macrofauna on the sediment surface was found higher in pre-monsoon, while *Gastropoda Optedicerus breviculum* (Pfeiffer, 1855), was the most abundant (RA=0.704). Important species index (ISI=70.36) and percentage of contribution (64.97%) were also found higher of this species than any others recorded from the site. The ANOSIM, Jaccard index and SIMPER analysis suggested that, the highest species abundance similarity was observed between pre-monsoon and monsoon, while the highest dissimilarity was observed between intermediate-September and pre-monsoon (74.67%). Seasonal PCA, nMDS, and cluster analysis revealed that pre-monsoon and monsoon were comparable in species and individual abundance. The dominance (0.85) was found significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in intermediate-September, while Simpson (0.7338), Shannon (1.56) and Evenness indices (0.5281) were found higher in monsoon followed by the higher Margalef richness indices (3.21) in post-monsoon. It was observed that, the seasonal ecological parameters were found significantly ($p < 0.05$) different, including the temperature, salinity, rainfall, nitrogenous compounds (NO_2 , NO_3 and NH_4), phosphorus compound (PO_4) and micro minerals. The Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) results suggested, a number of species was influenced by ecological factors. Considering the few studies on mangrove macrofauna in Malaysian Borneo, further research on their trophic structures and food web interactions are very important to be disclosed their overall characteristics and ecosystem functions.

Keywords: Intertidal mangrove, Gastropoda, Bivalvia, macrofauna, benthos